

A review on the causal structure of Black Hole models and Cosmological Singularity theorems

By Vaibhav kalvakota¹

ABSTRACT

Here, we will discuss these, by starting from Penrose Diagrams, and then to singularities. The Carter-Penrose Diagrams start by redefining the coordinate system with u, v defined by $(u, v) = (t-r, t+r)$ and Time-like and Light-like infinities. The range of u, v are taken to be in the usual range, $-\infty < u < \infty$ and $0 \leq v < \infty$. We will then further define the additional coordinates to cover the infinities with λ and ζ defined by $\lambda+\zeta = \tan^{-1} 2u$ and $\lambda-\zeta = \tan^{-1} 2v$. We will then discuss the Penrose diagram for a Minkowskian space-time. Then, we will take on to the Big Bang and Black Hole singularities, and the Reissner-Nordstrom Black hole model.

For the Penrose diagrams for a Schwarzschild Black hole, we will first define the Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates and Kruskal coordinates. Tortoise coordinates reads $r^* = r + 2GM \ln\left(\left|\frac{r}{2GM} - 1\right|\right)$ and then we will look deeper into the Schwarzschild metric, which reads $g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{R}\right), \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{R}\right)^{-1}, r^2, r^2(\sin \theta)^2\right)$. Then, we will discuss how we model the Nordstrom Black hole. Then, we will take a look at the Raychaudari Theorem and the Penrose theorems. We will talk about the causal structure of these models briefly, and finally conclude by talking about CTCs, or Closed Time-like Curves and models and examples of structures and conditions capable of housing the possibility of CTCs.

¹ Explorer1486@gmail.com.

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1: Defining Additional Coordinates:

1.1: The u, v coordinate system:

Let us take a look at the usual spherical metric, which reads

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (1)$$

We will define the coordinates u, v which satisfy the following relation:

$$-dt^2 + dr^2 = -dudv \quad (2)$$

In short, u, v are defined by the following set

$$v = t + r \quad (3)$$

$$u = t - r \quad (4)$$

We define the range of u, v to be $-\infty < u < \infty$ and $0 \leq v < \infty$. These are labelled as the “null” coordinates. This can be represented as the following figure:

Fig. 1: This shows the coordinates u, v . The extensions show that we need to add up another set of coordinates to cover the infinities.

Now, we have the following preliminary definitions of I^+, I^-, i^+, i^- , and i^0 :

1. i^+ This represents the future Time-like infinity
2. i^- This represents the past Time-like infinity
3. i^0 This represents the Space-like infinity
4. I^+ This represents the future null infinity
5. I^- This represents the past null infinity

In Fig. 1 the v extends to I^+ , while $-u$ extends to I^- . t extends downwards to i^- , while r does to i^0 . With that, we can say that i^+ extends as t approaches r at a fixed r , i^- extends as t approaches negative infinity at a fixed r , i^0 extends as r approaches infinity at a fixed t , I^+ extends as v approaches infinity at a fixed u , while I^- extends as u approaches negative infinity (to be considered is that each point in Fig 1 is a sphere of radius $\frac{1}{2}(v-u)$) at a fixed v .

This coordinate system needs to map *conformally*, which means we need to introduce another coordinate system to cover the entire manifold.

1.2: The λ, ζ coordinate system:

(In most texts, it is referred to as “the ψ, ζ system”, but I for some reason feel more obliged to λ).

We can easily define the λ, ζ system in terms of u, v via the following relations:

$$\lambda + \zeta = \tan^{-1} 2(t+r) = \tan^{-1} 2v \quad (5)$$

$$\lambda - \zeta = \tan^{-1} 2(t-r) = \tan^{-1} 2u \quad (6)$$

Using these relations, we can define the infinitesimal squared length element as

$$ds^2 = \phi^2(\lambda, \zeta)(-d\lambda^2 + d\zeta^2) + r^2(\lambda, \zeta)d\phi^2 \quad (7)$$

Here, we define

$$\phi^{-2}(\lambda, \zeta) = 4\cos^2 \frac{1}{2}(\lambda + \zeta)\cos^2 \frac{1}{2}(\lambda - \zeta) \quad (8)$$

Using this, we can define the changed value of $g_{\mu\nu}$ as the changed metric,
 $\widetilde{g}_{\mu\nu} = \phi^{-2} g_{\mu\nu}$.

With these systems set, we can now draw the Conformal diagram for a Minkowski space.

We can describe a Minkowskian 2-Sphere as the following diagram, where each point is a 2-sphere.

Fig 2: This shows a 2-Sphere at the given stationary r, t .

Our main consideration here will be on the Causal structure of a Black hole. We need to introduce the Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates and the Kruskal-Szekeres coordinates before we can move on.

2: The Eddington-Finkelstein coordinate system:

(I am in this text not setting the speed of light “ c ” to 1, so that all the terms will be straight-forward and clear. I hope this will clear and simplify all points. Note the Schwarzschild radius to be $R_{\text{Sch}} = 2GM/c^2$).

We are already familiar with the Schwarzschild metric, which reads out to

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 (1 - \frac{R_{sch}}{R}) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & (1 - \frac{R_{sch}}{R})^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2 \theta
 \end{array}$$

be , Now, we will consider the E-F

(Eddington-Finkelstein) Tortoise coordinate, which reads

$$r^* = r + 2GM \ln\left(\left|\frac{r}{2GM} - 1\right|\right) \quad (9)$$

We can see that (9) satisfies the slope condition,

$$\frac{dr^*}{dr} = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 R}\right)^{-1} \quad (10)$$

Note: r^* becomes infinitely huge as R approaches $2GM$. The following figure should help provide an idea of $R=2GM/c^2$ being the Event Horizon:

(The actual Event horizon is the collection of the world-lines of all Photon-like particles. This means that it is actually an enclosed sphere, whose surface is the collection of all the Light rays which can neither escape nor fall into the Black Hole. This is the set of all points at a distance of $r=2GM$ from the singularity. Also, the Event Horizon is a “Coordinate singularity”, which is different from the “Curvature Singularity” at $r=0$).

The Event Horizon is the collection of all light rays “trapped” at a distance of $R= 2GM/c^2$ from $R= 0$, the singularity.

Fig 3: The surface of the Black Hole is the set of all the light rays which are at a distance R_{Sch} from the Singularity, which means they can neither escape nor fall in towards the Singularity.

We can now set an elementary relation for r^* and the infinitesimal squared length equation as the following:

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 R}\right) (-dt^2 + dr^{*2}) + r^2 r^* (d\Omega^2) \quad (11)$$

The E-F coordinates have to do with the ingoing and outgoing null geodesics. We can write r^* in terms of the u, v system as $u = t - r^*$ and $v = t + r^*$.

Fig 4: The ingoing and outgoing null geodesics. Here, it is also portrayed the time-radius relation, which gives a deeper understanding of the Black Hole Horizon.²

3: The Kruskal-Szekeres coordinates:

One of the most beautiful coordinate system, this lays the total foundation of the Causal Structure of Black Holes. We will consider the relation between a simple singularity with the possibility of measurement, and how eventually considering the Kruskal Szekeres metric leads to a “naked Singularity”, which will be considered later.

² This image has been taken from David Ritz Finkelstein website: Eddington-Finkelstein Coordinates

Fig 4: The Kruskal Szekeres diagrams in divisions of four Hyperbolic quadrants. This diagram looks quite analogous to the Minkowski diagrams because of these being Light-Cone variant. As two hyperbolae approach from a distance “ r ” from quadrants III and I, they form a closed surface; after the last points in these quadrants they slip into quadrants II and IV.³

We will now take a look at the Kruskal-Szekeres set⁴, the range defined being $0 \leq r \leq \infty$ and $-\infty \leq ds^2 \leq \infty$.

$$\tilde{u} = -4Me^{-u/4M} \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{v} = 4Me^{v/4M} \quad (13)$$

Fig 5: The Kruskal Diagram for a Black Hole. The slant lines represent the Future and Past Event Horizons respectively.

³ This image has been taken from Wikipedia: Kruskal-Szekeres Coordinates. The example considered above in the picture considers a singularity system, whose values can be observed from the picture itself.

⁴ This set of equations for the Kruskal system has been considered from the document “Les Houches Lectures on Black Holes”.

The Kruskal-Szekeres metric is designated here as

$$ds^2 = Ze^{Z^{-1}} d\tilde{u}d\tilde{v} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (14)$$

Here, the value of Z is $\frac{-2GM}{r}$. With these done, we can now consider the exact meaning of the Penrose Diagrams.

4: Penrose Diagrams:

5: A Schwarzschild Black Hole:

The Penrose Diagrams can be constructed by simply considering the above concepts. The (Carter) Penrose diagram for a (non-rotating) Black Hole will be drawn as:

(Note: The idea of eternal Black Holes, or those gravitational singularities that form without a gravitational collapse is quite different. They do not have a collapsing mass indication, shown as a series of circles⁵ becoming progressively smaller and smaller, nor the “apparent” horizon formation from inside the star, the “real horizon” of which starts from the same point).

Fig 6: The Penrose diagram for a Black Hole. The Kruskal Coordinates are considered here, at their utmost importance. IV has a “White-Hole” singularity, a result of the “real” singularity in III back in the past.

⁵ Each circle actually refers to the star becoming smaller and therefore denser, often shown in texts as $\rho_0(r)$ to capture the relation between the density and the radius of the collapsing star.

With all the labels, the Penrose Diagram for a Schwarzschild Black Hole looks like

Fig 7⁶: The Penrose Diagram for a Schwarzschild Black Hole. As it can be observed, $r=2GM$ is a coordinate singularity, while $r=0$ is the curvature singularity.

There is a very beautiful point here: these diagrams preserve the nature of light-cones; they are at $\pm 45^\circ$ throughout the diagrams.

5.1: An example: The Reissner-Nordstrom Black hole model:

We will consider a particular type of Black Hole model, the Reissner Nordstrom black hole. In a simple way, it takes into consideration the charge of the event horizon, then by considering the relations of mass and charge on the $r=0$ and $r=2GM$ singularities. If we consider the Penrose diagram for a Schwarzschild Black hole, we observe the following:

(A Schwarzschild Black hole is quite simply a gravitational singularity formed by a gravitational collapse. The Schwarzschild metric does not take account of any charge on the Event Horizon, a basic concept used in the Reissner-Nordstrom model to explain the relations of M , the mass and Q , the charge.

⁶ Although it appears to be a 1+1 dimensional diagram, it is actually 3+1, referring to the fact that we have set the condition for Spherical Symmetry. We have therefore mapped it into a 1+1 dimensional diagram, hiding the other two symmetric dimensions.

At $M=Q$, we observe the possibility of a “naked singularity”, a prominent point we will only briefly discuss in this paper)

Fig 8⁷: Penrose diagram for a Black hole depicting the collapse of the star.

We will first take a look at the Nordstrom metric,

$$ds^2 = -U(r)dt^2 + U(r)^{-1}dr^2 + r^2d\Omega^2 \quad (15)$$

Here, we define $U(r)$ as the changed Schwarzschild parameter:

$$U(r) = \left(1 - \frac{R_{Sch}}{R} + \frac{Q^2}{R^2}\right) \quad (16)$$

We will also label the following relations:

$$r_+ = GM + \sqrt{M^2 + Q^2} \quad (17)$$

$$r_- = GM - \sqrt{M^2 - Q^2} \quad (18)$$

A point to note here is that by introducing $U(r)$, we have set the Event Horizon to be the collection of all points whose result is that $U(r)$ sums to be zero. But, (17, 18) results in *two slightly different* Horizons, which means we need to tweak (15) into the following:

⁷ Now, this is a clear depiction of a non-eternal black hole. The curve that extends from the bottom (i^-) is the collapsing star. For an eternal black hole, this is not depicted.

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{R_+}{R}\right)\left(1 - \frac{R_-}{R}\right) dt^2 + \left(\left(1 - \frac{R_+}{R}\right)\left(1 - \frac{R_-}{R}\right)\right)^{-1} + d\sigma \quad (19)$$

Here, $d\sigma$ is equal to $r^2 d\Omega^2$. Notice how at $M < Q$, the singularity will not be covered by a Horizon. Therefore, in order to preserve the Cosmic Censorship Hypothesis, we set $M \geq Q$, so as to prevent a naked singularity. Although we can extend the working of Nordstrom-Reissner model with ADS correspondence⁸, we will not consider that in this text.

6: The Big Bang Singularity:

(This is a very huge subject and I have merely provided a small review of what exactly it implies).

6.1: From the FRW metric:

Recall the Friedmann-Robertson-Lemaitre-Walker metric, which considers the function,

$$S_k(r) = \begin{cases} k^{-1/2} \sin rk^{1/2} & (k > 0) \\ r & (k = 0) \\ k^{-1/2} \sinh rk^{1/2} & (k < 0) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Here, the Radius of Curvature is defined as $R_{\text{Curv}} = k^{-1/2}$, which should suffice to clear what exactly k is. The Friedmann-Robertson equation reads

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a(t)^2 [dr^2 + f_k(r)^2 r^2 (d\Omega^2)] \quad (21)$$

Here, in equation (18). We notice that $a(t)$ already has it's value specified in the Friedmann equation⁹,

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho + \frac{kx^2}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} \quad (22)$$

⁸ Check reference [7][e] for more information on R-N and ADS-CFT relations.

⁹ The original equation Alexander Friedmann had written down was of the form, $\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho$. Eventually, the Cosmological Constant paved way for the changed Friedmann Equation that is specified here as (22).

Here, Λ is the Cosmological constant. For an Einstein *Static* universe, we set $\dot{a} = \ddot{a} = 0$, thereby reducing the Friedmann equation to the simplified form which reads in terms of the density, pressure and the cosmological constant. This model was designed to model a very simple *homogeneous* and *isotropic* universe.

The most interesting thing about results arising from a model such as the FRWL model is that we can easily find a trivial set of solutions. For instance, if we were to identify $R(t) = x\{a(t)\}$, we can easily find the Friedmann equations to result to

$$\frac{1}{2}\{\dot{R}(t)\}^2 = \frac{GM}{R} + \frac{\Lambda}{6}R^2 - \frac{1}{2}kc^2x^2 \quad (23)$$

Which can be identified from the Friedmann equation in the second order derivative of acceleration,

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = (-1)\frac{4\pi G}{3}\left(\rho + \frac{3p}{c^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3}\right) \quad (24)$$

Here, “p” is the pressure. Also, in the scaling to cold matter and ultra-hot matter¹⁰ (C.M and U.H.M respectively), we follow that there holds the proportionality of density and the reciprocal of the third degree of acceleration, $\rho \propto \frac{1}{a^3}$, or $\rho = \frac{\nu}{a^3}$. Now, we will introduce the types of curvature allowed.

There are three types of curvatures that we can model in our theory. Positive, zero, or negative.

1. Positive can be thought using the triangle experiment. If you were to draw a triangle on a surface with positive curvature, then the sum of it's interior angles will exceed 180.
2. Zero refers to the surface whose nature is such that the sum of angles in a triangle laid on it's surface is exactly 180
3. Negative refers to the surface whose nature is such that the sum of angles in a triangle laid on it's surface will be less than 180.

In general, the general equation for the comparisons can be laid out to be

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + (a(t))^2 d\Gamma^2 \quad (25)$$

¹⁰ We also consider radiation under the same category as that of U.H.M or Ultra-Hot matter.

Here, $d\Gamma$ is a Riemann manifold, which is *homogeneous* and *isotropic*. Recalling the function of k , we will write down the FR metric generalised to depict curvature,

$$d\Gamma^2 = (1 - r^2k)^{-1}dr^2 + r^2d\Omega^2 \quad (26)$$

We generalise the value of k to be +1 for S^3 , 0 for R^3 and -1 for H^3 .

6.2: Singularities and enclosed causal structures:

We will start by considering the expansion¹¹ equation,

$$\theta = \nabla_\mu v^\mu \quad (27)$$

We also need the Time-like Causal convergence condition,

$$R_{\mu\nu\sigma}^\sigma v^\mu v^\nu \geq 0 \quad (28)$$

The Raychaudari-Komar singularity theorem for a perfect fluid satisfying the Stress-Energy-Momentum-Density Tensor equation

$$T = \zeta v_\mu v_\nu + p(g_{\mu\nu} + v_\mu v_\nu) \quad (29)$$

(Here ζ represents the Energy-density) reads as the following:

“If the expansion (27) is positive and the convergence condition specified as (28) is also satisfied, then the value of ζ diverges along the length of v^μ in the finite future of the fluid, provided it also necessarily satisfies $v^\mu v_\mu = -1$ ”.

This was the first singularity theorem specified in terms of a fluid system. The Penrose singularity theorem (which eventually lead to Stephen Hawking proposing the Big Bang Time-reversal singularity model) read in terms of a closed trapped surface and the Cauchy Hypersurface relation, which meant that null geodesic incompleteness could be modelled. This holds *if and only if* all null geodesics satisfy the θ convergence condition, along with the Energy condition. This is a consideration of the working of singularities involving non-

¹¹ There is also the concept of *Closed Trapped Surfaces*, which are defined using an expansion quite similar to this. It considers the future directed affine parametrized null geodesics fields v_\pm and then by considering these values in the relation (27). The $+\theta$ is less than 0, also the same for $-\theta$. An alternative explanation is to draw a sphere, then a plane tangential to it at a point “p”, then by drawing the perpendicular to it. This gives the normal basis to the sphere “ \mathcal{M} ” and then considering the light rays convergence.

compact Cauchy Hypersurface, and also equipping the Spacetime with a closed future trapped surface. Later, Stephen Hawking and Roger Penrose together modelled the Penrose Hawking Singularity theorem, which stated simply reads “If the expansion of theta and the generic condition holds, then there exists a geodesic incompleteness considering at least one of the trio- a closed chroral hypersurface, a closed trapped surface or a point with a converging lightcone at least twice” (This involves the reconsideration of a *trapped submanifold*).

We will also define the Causal structure with the following definitions which underlie the points above:

The Time-like future of a point $p \in M$ is the collection of all points $q \in M$ such that a future directed Time-like curve exists that joins p and q. This is represented as I^+ we have already used in our discussion of Penrose Diagrams

The Causal future of a point $p \in M$ is the collection of all points given $q \in M$ such that a future directed Causal curve joins p and q. This is represented as J^+ .

The corresponding definitions of the Time-like past and Causal past are defined in a similar way, with I^- and J^- .

There reads the important *generic condition* defined for a Time-like 4-vector v^μ as the following inequality:

$$R_{\alpha\beta\gamma\mu} v^\beta v^\gamma \geq 0 \quad (30)$$

This is usually never violated, but an example is the Einstein universe.

The Einstein static universe model violates our intuition defined for the generic condition. It satisfies the expansion relation, is globally hyperbolic, but violates the fact that there should exist an *incompleteness*. It is a system with *geodesic completeness*.

Also, there is the *Cosmic Censorship Hypothesis*. It states that no singularity can exist without forming an Event Horizon. Although from the Kerr model, if we could spin it by a ratio compared to the square of the mass of the Black hole, we can isolate the singularity. Also, in the Reissner-Nordstrom model, we saw how at $M < Q$ we observe a naked singularity. But, these have their own preventive measures. For instance, introducing charges to a Nordstrom Black hole would mean repulsion between charges, and also increased mass, thereby differing again. The same happens for a Kerr Black hole, only with angular momentum instead of charge and a little difference in the interpretation of

increasing horizon. These preserve the Cosmic Censorship. So, we are still a little further from a model that violates the Cosmic Censorship Hypothesis. There is two parts- *weak*, involving just the impossibility of a naked singularity, and *strong*, putting forward the impossibility of non-Time-like singularities.

We will on a final note discuss the idea of Closed Time-like Curves.

6.3: Closed Time-like Curves (CTCs):

The causality condition is such that nobody can retrace their own past. In fact, the name should quite clear it, because all massive particles are defined to be Time-like. This has implications in many ideas revolving around causal loops. For instance, if you were to go back in time to stop your present from happening, then simply that is why your present is such. You simply cannot commute back in time. Also, this also ensures the existence of maximal proper time between two events. So, we now state the Causal conditions as *“the system of principle that both prevent a particle from tracing it’s past, and also maximising the length of proper time between two events”*. Now, the idea actually appears vague, because you have to draw a model, which may or may not house the possibility of CTCs arising. But, it is not. Instead, GR predicts mathematical models such as Godel’s model of the Universe to instead control how exactly mathematically you can prove the existence of CTCs. For example, the weak energy condition defined by the following inequality which considers Time-like vector form:

$$T_{\mu\nu}v^{\mu}v^{\nu} \geq 0 \quad (31)$$

One of the first considerations of the Einstein field equations containing CTCs is the Van Stockum Space-time. It starts by the consideration of an infinitely long cylinder of dust rotating, imposing also the cylindrical symmetry condition. Then, by taking into account the angular momentum and radius relation, we get the inequality to generate CTCs for this model as $\omega r > 1/2$ for the rotating cylinder. This can be easily identified from the Van Stockum metric.

Another consideration involving the generations of CTCs is the violation of Causality. This can be achieved using those solutions to the Einstein field equation that generate CTCs, thereby also confining a violation of Causality. Instead of defining the metric *for* a model, we can instead reverse engineer, by first constructing a metric which generates the possibility of CTCs and then

trace it back to the model. This is quite simple, quite analogous to how we derived the Schwarzschild Black hole model from the Schwarzschild metric.

The Causal structure of any model generating CTCs is quite interesting, considering the fact that their implications are huge. Firstly, CTCs are very important in terms of causal intuition, because this would mean that there exists some form of violation of the Causal conditions. Secondly, this also means that a model containing a causal loop may exist.

Conclusion

In this review paper we have sketched the big picture of Causal structures in a nutshell, from Penrose Diagrams, to the Reissner-Nordstrom model, to the concept of singularity theorems and geodesic incompleteness. We have also taken a glance at CTCs, and what their modelling looks like, and a bird's eye view of the Godel's model, and the Van Stockum model. Also, we have discussed about the modelling of Singularities. The structure of Causality has been the key throughout this paper, and we have reviewed their important implications that arise in General Relativity and different structures.

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